

SLOT-DIE COATING OF CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS AND CHITOSAN FOR AN IMPROVED BARRIER PROPERTIES OF PAPER

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Abstract. *Nanocellulose and chitosan (Cht) are the two most abundant naturally produced biopolymers and are being extensively studied as candidates for renewable oxygen and water vapour barrier films used in food packaging. However, rare studies have been performed by using a scalable, inexpensive, and relatively fast continuous coating processes. In this work, the feasibility of cellulose nanocrystal (CNC) and Cht coating, as an individual or a hybrid mixture in a single or bi-layer process, was studied by using a slot-die technique. The effect of CNC/Cht solid content and the coating parameters (injection/coating speed and wet thickness applied) on the quantity (dry weight, g/m²), homogeneity, wettability and barrier properties of the paper is studied by evaluating its thickness, whiteness, air and water-vapour permeabilities.*

Keywords: Barrier properties, nanocellulose, chitosan, slot-die coating, paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Besides of nanocellulose, the most abundant biopolymer in nature, other polysaccharides such as chitosan, starch, pectin and alginate, have been extensively studied as candidates for the preparation of biodegradable and renewable films and coatings, able of exerting a barrier effect to oxygen and

water vapour (Grimaldi et al. 2022), following the circular economy and sustainability (Kumar et al. 2021).

The combination of CNCs as reinforcement and filler with polysaccharides have shown to significantly lowers oxygen permeability of the films due to the formation of a network that connects via hydrogen bonds (Saxena et al. 2010). It has also been observed that the addition of CNC in chitosan (Cht) influences on water vapour permeability, which decrease with increasing CNC content (Khan et al. 2012). Many coating techniques, including filtration, rod/barrier coating, blade coating, spray coating and tear-off coating (Lavoine et al. 2014; Mazhari Mousavi et al. 2017 & 2018, Juhant 2021) on paper substrates, have been performed to improve their resistance and barrier effect (Tayeb et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2018). Although these techniques are efficient with good coating deposition, the low solids content of highly viscous solutions often requires multiple layers of deposition to achieve good barrier effects (Cranston et al. 2008; Satam et al. 2018).

Slot-die coating is a scalable, continuous, inexpensive and relatively fast (up to several m/sec) continuous deposition technique, that enables an uniform and controlled deposition of thin layer coatings over the entire surface of a moving substrate. Both low and high viscosity solutions, including nanocellulose suspensions (Kumar et al. 2018), can be used, and a wide range of thicknesses (from 20 nm up to few 100 μm) can be deposited by modulating the process parameters (such as coating speed, flow rate, slot-gap), solution properties (surface tension, water retention, viscosity) and drying temperature.

In this work, slot-die deposition technique was used to apply CNC suspension and Cht solution onto plain/un-modified paper substrate in order to improve their barrier properties, focusing on wettability (contact angle), air permeability and moisture transport. The effect of the established coating parameters (injection speed and wet tickness) in a single (monolayer) and bi-layer deposition was investigated by coating quantity (g/m^2), thickness (μm) and homogeneity (whiteness) of the applied coating.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Chitosan (MW: 310,000-375,00; Deacetylation grade >75%) and acetic acid (HOAc, ACS grade) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO, USA). CNC (containing 253.5 ± 7.5 mmol/kg of sulphate groups) was purchased from CelluForce (Canada, production #2015-011) in the form of a fine powder. The

plane uncoated paper (44 ± 2 g/m², 65 ± 2 μm) from industrial production was used.

2. 2 Preparation of suspensions

Three water-based suspensions with different total solid contents of CNC vs. Cht were prepared: 11 wt% CNC (50 dPas), 2 wt% Cht solution prepared with 1 % of acetic acid (52 dPas), and mixture of 5.5 wt% CNC and 1 wt % Cht (25 dPas). To all suspensions, 20 wt/wt % sorbitol was added as plasticizer.

2. 3 Slot-die coating

The Challenger 175, semi-pilot & automated S2S coating unit (Norbert Schläfli nsm AG, Switzerland) with inline integrated 190 mm wide slot-die module (TSE Troller AG, Switzerland) and NIR drying station (NIR252-125 Adphos GmbH, Germany) was used to control the speed of the substrate, the flow rate of injected solutions, and the drying power/time. The slot-die shim of 180 μm thickness was used, while the distance between the substrate and the slot was 75 μm. The injection/flow speed of the suspension/solution was set in the range between 5 and 80 mL/min (corresponding to the substrate speed between 0.3 and 2.4 m/min), depending on the viscosity of the suspension/solution, while the thickness of the wet deposited layer were in the range between 5 and 12.5 μm. The drying was performed at 5 m/min using 6x1.2 kW emitter power.

2. 4 Characterization

Water retention properties of the suspensions/solution and the paper were evaluated with the updated method of (Abo Akademi, 1989). The paper thickness (gauge meter) and weight increase (gravimetrically), air (Bendtsen, ISO 5636-3:2014) and water vapor permeability (WVP at $23\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $50\pm 5\%$ RH; MultiPerme srl, ISO 15106-2), CIE whiteness (ISO 11475:2004) and surface wetting (contact angle, OCA 15EC, DataPhysics Instruments, ASTM D5725-99) were determined.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As seen from the Figure 1, the paper thickness increased slightly with injection speed for all wet-thickness settings, and was the most significant for CNC+Cht (5.5+1 wt%) mixture resulting to an increase from 27.6% (at 19 mL/min injection speed) to 39.3 % (38 mL/min) at 5 to 10 μm wet thickness setting (0.323-0.489 g/m² dry weigh applied), that reduced the air permeability from around 30 to 7 mL/min. In the case of 11 wt% CNC suspension, the air permeability of the paper

was depended (decreasing) primarily on the wet thickness setting and secondarily on the injection speed; the air permeability thus reduced from 51.8 to 25.3 mL/min at 7.5 μm wet thickness (0.827 g/m^2 dry weigh), and from 8.47 to 0.013 mL/min at 10 μm wet thickness (1.150 g/m^2 dry weigh) by increasing the injection speed from 21.4 to 35.6 mL/min and from 28.5 to 76 mL/min, respectively. However, similiary low air permeability (3 mL/min) was obtained for pure 2 wt% Cht solution at much lower solid applied (up to 0.323 g/m^2) resulting to a slightly increased (2-14%) paper thickness.

Figure 1. Effect of slot-die coating of different CNC-based suspensions and Cht solution on increasing dry paper thickness and air permeability, depending on the coating parameter setting (injection speed (ml/min) and wet thickness (μm)).

The dewatering is an important aspect of a coating process, influences on both the runnability/coatability and the drying originate from the interaction between the base paper and the water phase of the coating suspension/solution. As seen from the results collected in Table 1, the water retention of 2 wt% Cht solution is much higher (749 g/m^2) compared to 11 wt% CNC suspension (152 g/m^2) and is almost completely retained by the paper when applied on it. While the increase of paper thickness (Figure 1) for all Cht coated samples was generally much lower (between 2-14%) as compared to the CNC coated ones (17-25%), this mean that the Cht solution penetrating better into the bulk structure of the paper while CNC remained mainly on its surface; The Cht coated paper also required longer time to dry (even up to 6 passes have been required for NIR drying). Relatively lower water retention (213 g/m^2) of half-less concentrated mixture of CNC+Cht (5.5+1 wt%) can thus be due to electrostatic interactions

between negatively charged/sulphonated CNC and positive/aminated Cht, resulting to its networking and deposition mainly on the outer surface of the paper.

These conclusions are supported by barrier and wetting properties of the coated paper. The uncoated paper was highly permeable for water vapour, so WVTR tests failed, although the CA was relatively high (85°) as compared to the CNC coated samples (CA is reduced up to 39° by increasing the coating speed), confirming the retention of highly hydrophilic CNC mainly on the surface, while reducing the air permeability (from 51.8 to 0.01 mL/min) and increasing the whiteness by better distribution of CNC over the paper surface. On the other hand, as expected, the more diply penetrating Cht increased the hydrophobicity of the paper (102°), while also reducing the air permeability (3 mL/min). The mixture of CNC and Cht did not have a significant effect on any of the properties, probably due to low solid content and inadequate weight ratio between them. In the opposite, the 2-layer coated sample (CNC applied before the Cht) thus resulted to CA of 93° and no air permeability. It can be concluded that both CNC and Cht contribute to the air permeability reduction, where CNC generating a highly H-bonded network with the paper, while eletrostatic interaction with the Cht applied on top, reducing the paper surface wettability.

The deviation in the WVTR may also be explained from the decreased uniformity of both the paper and the coated layer leading to pores or defects on the measured surface.

*Table 1. Whiteness, contact angle, water-vapour and air permeability of paper after slot-die coating of different suspensions/solution. *Sample was too permeable, could not me measured.*

Suspension/ solution Water retention of susp./sol. & the paper (g/m²)	Coating parameters seting	Coated dry weight (g/m²)	Whiteness CIE	Contact angle / CA (°)	WVTR (g/m²d)	Air permeability (mL/min)
<i>Uncoated</i>	/	0	77.94	85.00	*	287.2
<i>11CNC (50 dPas) 152 & 13 g/m² Δ=139 g/m²</i>	<i>21.38 mL/min 7.5 μm</i>	<i>0.827</i>	<i>90.78</i>	<i>51.73</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>51.8</i>
	<i>35.63 mL/min 7.5 μm</i>		<i>92.71</i>	<i>48.36</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>25.3</i>
	<i>28.5 mL/min 10 μm</i>	<i>1.150</i>	<i>92.27</i>	<i>50.28</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>8.47</i>
	<i>38 mL/min 10 μm</i>		<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>1.1</i>
	<i>76 mL/min 10 μm</i>		<i>93.87</i>	<i>39.83</i>	<i>45.98</i>	<i>0.013</i>
	<i>19 mL/min</i>	<i>0.323</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>29.94</i>

5.5CNC+1Cht (25 dPas) 213 & 19 g/m ² Δ=194 g/m ²	5 μm					
	28.5 mL/min 7.5 μm	0.489	76.52	85.60	67.55	19.7
2Cht (52 dPas) 749 & 10 g/m ² Δ=739 g/m ²	9.5 mL/min 10 μm	0.226	79.61	101.8	50.42	3.0
11CNC/2Cht-5	CNC: 38 mL/min - 10 μm	1.15 + 1.35	75.36	74.24	70.26	0
11CNC/2Cht-7.5	Cht: 20 mL/min - 5/7.5 μm		75.36	93.38	71.16	0

4 CONCLUSIONS

A homogenous thin layer deposition of CNC (1.15 g/m²) and Cht (1.35 g/m²) were formed on paper substrate by slot-die coating, resulted to no air permeability compared to the untreated sample at 2-layer deposited sample. The surface wettability was also reduced (CA 93°) and the moisture permeability decreases to around 70 g/m²d. This investigation shows that the barrier properties of a plane/untreated paper after a thin-layer deposition of CNC and Cht can be significantly improved, opening a way for the production of a paper with biodegradable coatings based on natural materials.

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